

Exhaustive Prompting: New Method for Boosting Accuracy

Jihyeon Yoon

(Amateur Mathematician, somehowme@gmail.com, flyingtext@nate.com)

September 29, 2024

Abstract

This paper aims to introduce new method for forcing logical thinking to AI by delicate instruction prompting with multiple executions. exhaustive prompting uses general reasoning formation to force the way of thinking to the AI by accomodating of essential factors in prompting. With this new methodology, accuracy in well-known benchmarks has been boosted up at 1.0%p to 9.7%p.

1 Introduction

Current methodology in gaining performance of LLM(Large Language Model)s is focused on enlarging parameters of the model. This method has background that the larger the model size, more the knowledge the model can accomodate. But it is questionable that is it really true to be in any occasion. If only the size matters to the performance, ENIAC can still be a high performance computer. But in reality it is not. Rather, it is quite a problem when performance and the model size does not correlate in linear way. And current benchmark test scores show the gap between the least linearity.

As said, it is job of benchmark dataset to figure out the performance of the given model. Well-known benchmarks are used to evaluate the performance of the LLM models. The benchmarks that will be discussed in this paper can be such as ARC-Challenge, SCRUPLES and ETHICS.

In this paper, I will introduce set theory based new method “exhaustive prompting” which can be applied in prompting to boost the accuracy and related efficieny up to the targeted task.

2 Methodology and Background

2.1 Core Idea in Mathematical Forcing

Exhaustive prompting has come upon the similar idea in mathematics, especially set theory. In set theory, forcing method is used to reason whether the principality can be set up indepedently without being dependent with other axioms or principles. Exhaustive prompting is in extension to the understanding of approach. There are two main indenpendencies that Paul Cohen’s forcing method suggests:

1. Independency in exclusion: although being excluded in set of existing axioms, the principality (existence and uniqueness) of the statement must be reasonable independently.
2. Independency in inclusion: although being included in set of existing axioms, the principality (existence and uniqueness) of the existing statement must be reasonable independently.

These independencies fit in the condition of compactness in any axiomatic system. For the example of independency in exclusion, if there is an existing axiom set contains principle statement that calls cat as a tiger, but if with excluding principle statement that calling cat as a tiger makes contradiction in the other principle statements, it makes a breach in the independency in exclusion. And for example of independency in inclusion, if there are existing axioms set that cat cannot be a tiger, but with adding axiom that calling Siberian tiger as a cat makes a breach in the independency in inclusion.

These two kinds of independency are core concepts in mathematical forcing in set theory[Cohen(2002)].

2.2 Application of Mathematical Forcing to Exhaustive Prompting

So what is exhaustive prompting? It is prompting statement with LLM to force essential and general property in logics that can be found in any entity in nature. For direct example like used prompting method in this paper, 5W1H can be a good pillar. For given “prompt”:

1. Execution in what: Explain what “prompt” mainly demands.
2. Execution in who: Explain who “prompt” mainly demands.
3. Execution in where: Explain where “prompt” mainly demands.
4. Execution in when: Explain when “prompt” mainly demands.
5. Execution in why: Explain why “prompt” mainly demands.
6. Execution in how: Explain how “prompt” mainly demands.
7. Final execution: Answer the demands in overall.

With core idea that mathematical forcing demands description in independent form, what(entity), who(agent), where(place), when(time), why(reason), and how(method) can play unique and distinct roles in constitution of general logic formation. This logical forcing makes unthinkable to be thinkable within execution of prompts, making diversification within plausible answers in the LLM.

And it is important to say that 5W1H is only just one of the examples in exhaustive prompting methodology. There can be other many generalizations in approaching general, or specialized tasks.

2.3 Computational Background

For this research, I used Ollama with Gemma2 2B FP16 model[Team et al.(2024)Team, Riviere, Pathak, Sessa, Hardin, Bhupatiraja]

3 Benchmarks in Exhaustive Prompting

3.1 ETHICS Justice dataset

ETHICS dataset is one of the dataset that can be applied for assessment in given scenario’s ethical aspect[Hendrycks et al.(2021)Hendrycks, Burns, Spitzer, Sastry, Soudry, and Shih]. In this testing for ETHICS dataset on the justice, cases of test set and hard test set will be discussed. In this evaluation, model temperature was set to 0.

	ALBERT-xx-large	RoBERTa-large	BERT-large	BERT-base	GPT-3 (few-shot)	Word Averaging	Random Baseline
Justice Test Case	59.9	56.7	32.7	26.0	15.2	10.3	6.3
Justice Hard Test Case	38.2	38.0	11.3	7.6	11.9	6.6	6.3

Table 1: Comparison of different methods on the ETHICS dataset

As Table 3.1 is of 2021, there can be further improvements in newer models in current year 2024. So, to evaluate reasoning by comparison, I conducted evaluation on the test cases vanilla method with exhaustive prompting in comparison.

	Justice - Vanilla	Justice - exhaustive prompting
Test Case	0.588	0.642
Hard Test Case	0.563	0.622

Table 2: Comparison of vanilla questioning with exhaustive prompting methodology in ETHICS dataset

In test case there was 5.4% improvement and in hard test case 5.9% improvement overall accuracy.

The specific prompts used in this evaluation are as follow:

For vanilla method:

[Answer in one short sentence] Regarding following situations, is this scenario ethical? Answer in only yes or no. [Scenario] (Scenario Text Here)

For exhaustive prompting method:

[Answer in one short sentence] Tell me when or why or what or where or who or how the following contents can happen: (Scenario Text Here)

With six executions(when, why, what, where, who, and how) of upper evaluation, then next.

[Answer in one short sentence] Regarding following situations, is it justifiable to not too much, or not too less virtue? Answer in only yes or no.
[Background] (When or why or what or where or who or how result Here)
[Scenario] (Scenario Text Here)

Another six evaluations are done with each six structuralized background. Then with counting ratio of yes in total answers, whether the justice or not is judged.

3.2 SCRUPLES dataset

In this evaluation, model temperature was set to 0. There was 2.6% improvement overall in SCRUPLES dataset test case accuracy.

	SCRUPLES - Vanilla	SCRUPLES - exhaustive prompting
Test Case	0.499	0.509

Table 3: Comparison of vanilla questioning with exhaustive prompting methodology in SCRUPLES dataset

In SCRUPLES dataset, the same evaluation was done with ETHICS Justice dataset with text and binarized label columns[Lourie et al.(2020)Lourie, Bras, and Choi].

3.3 ARC-Challenge dataset

In this evaluation, model temperature was set to the default value. ARC-Challenge dataset is benchmark about scientific questions in choices[Clark et al.(2018)Clark, Cowhey, Etzioni, Khot, Sabharwal, Schoenick, and Tafjord]. There was 1.0% improvement overall in ARC-Challenge dataset test case accuracy.

	ARC-Challenge - Vanilla	ARC-Challenge - exhaustive prompting
Test Case	0.554	0.651

Table 4: Comparison of vanilla questioning with exhaustive prompting methodology in ARC-Challenge dataset

For the evaluation result in vanilla method, it was referenced after Google’s official homepage model card[Team(2024)]. For exhaustive prompting:

Evaluate the statement to the question in aspect of when, why, where, what, who, and how can be correct with probabilistically suggesting correct possibility percentage. Only output possibility percentage(%) and the explanation itself. Do not output more than the possibility percentage number. Question: (Question Text Here)
Statement: (Each Choice Here)

With evaluating four choices in the question, lastly executes:

(Each Evaluated Possibility and Explananation Choice Here)
Select the correct choice for the question that fits the intention of the question.
Output Format : [Choice N]
Only output the correct choice in upper format.

4 Discussion

This result has two main implications.

1. Even with small parameter sized models, it has more possibility than the first suggested benchmarks, which monotonically applying the task. Specifically with exhaustive prompting, the model improves drastically.
2. Prioritized many executions can lead to improvement in benchmark score in specialized tasks.

4.1 Relation of exhaustive prompting with Set Theory

As mentioned in background section, exhaustive prompting focuses on giving logical boundaries to the given task. This is similar to the concept of forcing in set theory. For example, this paper tried exhaustive prompting in 5W1H formation.

Each item in 5W1H is independent in inclusion or exclusion. This is similar to well-known MECE(Mutually Exclusive Collectively Exhaustive) concept but more comprehensive. MECE concept does not specify each role in its exhaustiveness, so to say, how the exhaustiveness can be driven. This can make the result empirically work overall but not extensive in its alignment. But forcing in set theory not only focuses on its exclusion, but also with the case assumed to be included.

4.2 Implication of Improvement in ARC-Challenge Score

Improvements in ARC-Challenge almost reached the level of 9B parameter model(with exhaustive prompting 68.4% accuracy) only with 2B parameter model(with exhaustive prompting 65% accuracy). This means question quality and repeated aggregated information in execution matters to the performance in result, almost high as 4 times to the size of model parameters. This implies current tries in achieving more higher fundamental in benchmark score have to not only focus on the size of the model, but how the input has to become in the pre- or multiple-processing.

5 Data and Codes

Data and code is available at Github repository(<https://github.com/flyingtext/exhaustive-prompting>). Any feedback or question for the research is appreciated.

6 Acknowledgement

This paper’s part of research in scoring evaluation process was done with Anthropic Claude 3.5 Sonnet model online.

References

- [Clark et al.(2018)Clark, Cowhey, Etzioni, Khot, Sabharwal, Schoenick, and Tafjord] Peter Clark, Isaac Cowhey, Oren Etzioni, Tushar Khot, Ashish Sabharwal, Carissa Schoenick, and Oyvind Tafjord. Think you have solved question answering? try arc, the ai2 reasoning challenge. *arXiv:1803.05457v1*, 2018.
- [Cohen(2002)] Paul Cohen. The discovery of forcing. *The Rocky Mountain journal of mathematics*, 32(4):1071–1100, 2002.
- [Hendrycks et al.(2021)Hendrycks, Burns, Basart, Critch, Li, Song, and Steinhardt] Dan Hendrycks, Collin Burns, Steven Basart, Andrew Critch, Jerry Li, Dawn Song, and Jacob Steinhardt. Aligning ai with shared human values. *Proceedings of the International Conference on Learning Representations (ICLR)*, 2021.
- [Lourie et al.(2020)Lourie, Bras, and Choi] Nicholas Lourie, Ronan Le Bras, and Yejin Choi. Scruples: A corpus of community ethical judgments on 32,000 real-life anecdotes. *arXiv e-prints*, 2020.
- [Team(2024)] Gemma Team. Gemma. 2024. doi: 10.34740/KAGGLE/M/3301. URL <https://www.kaggle.com/m/3301>.

[Team et al.(2024)Team, Riviere, Pathak, Sessa, Hardin, Bhupatiraju, Hussenot, Mesnard, Shahriari, Ramé, et al.]
Gemma Team, Morgane Riviere, Shreya Pathak, Pier Giuseppe Sessa, Cassidy Hardin, Surya Bhupatiraju, Léonard Hussenot, Thomas Mesnard, Bobak Shahriari, Alexandre Ramé, et al. Gemma 2: Improving open language models at a practical size. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2408.00118*, 2024.